

CVIc: A web platform for automated Coastal Vulnerability Index-based assessment

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ABSTRACT

Intensifying climate change impacts, such as Sea-Level Rise (SLR), floods, extreme weather events and coastal erosion, threaten ecosystems, infrastructure, and human communities at a global scale, making vulnerability assessments a crucial prerequisite for identifying areas necessitating urgent and effective actions. The Coastal Vulnerability Index (CVI) is a widely used index-based methodology for such assessments; yet its implementation often relies on complex, manual workflows across multiple proprietary desktop Geographic Information Systems (GIS) software. Existing approaches limit accessibility, lack transparency, hinder reproducibility, and are frequently time-consuming. To address these challenges, CVIc (Coastal Vulnerability Index Compiler) is presented herein as a novel, open-source, and open-access geoprocessing web application for the computation of the CVI. CVIc provides an end-to-end dynamic workflow, guiding users from shoreline data import to the application of various standardized indices (CVI, ICVI). CVIc is deployed as a website (<https://alexandrosliaskos.github.io/CVIc/>) and features interactive tools for shoreline digitization, segmentation, parameter value assignment, and visualization and export of results. The only input requirements are a shoreline Shapefile input or a GeoTIFF image for digitization, and the knowledge of the spatial distribution of the parameter values for the area under study. By leveraging IndexedDB for browser-based data storage, CVIc operates without server-side dependencies, ensuring data privacy, protection and large-scale dataset processing. To our knowledge, this consists the first web solution of its kind, as its streamlined approach into a unified and user-friendly platform makes this type of analysis more feasible to researchers and coastal practitioners, while providing policymakers with more accessible and robust data for decision-making. Its open-source nature enables community-driven advancements, and the simple User Interface (UI) and map components mark it as appropriate for educational purposes.

1. Introduction

Climate change is accelerating coastal changes with projections indicating further intensification throughout the coming decades (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), 2023a, 2023b). As coastal regions face an unprecedented combination of climate-driven threats (Hermkens et al., 2025), the urgent need for comprehensive vulnerability assessment has never been more critical (Cabana et al., 2023). The year 2024 alone witnessed 393 natural disasters globally, resulting in 16,753 fatalities and \$320 billion in economic losses (CRED, 2025a). This significant challenge presents a serious global threat to coastal zones (Ghoms et al., 2024), though its manifestations vary significantly across regions. While the worldwide average for sea-level

rise is a concerning 4.5 mm per year, areas like the Indo-Pacific and the Caribbean are witnessing alarming rates nearing 10 mm annually (Calvin et al., 2023; WMO, 2025). However, this relentless rise is just one aspect of the danger; coastal communities are increasingly impacted by several intensifying hazards. Extreme weather events are gathering more destructive force, floods are becoming more commonplace, erosion is rapidly reshaping shorelines, and saltwater is pushing further into vital freshwater resources (Hernández-Delgado, 2024; Laino et al., 2024) (see Table 1).

The devastating consequences of extreme weather phenomena are already clearly visible: recent cyclones have caused severe damage in the Philippines, Malawi, Mozambique, and Bangladesh, while low-lying island nations like Tuvalu, a country in the West-Central Pacific Ocean,

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Table 1
A hierarchical taxonomy of Coastal Vulnerability Assessment (CVA).

Level	Term	Role	Components
L1	Analytical Purpose	Goal-centric	Coastal Vulnerability Assessment (CVA)
L2	Methodological framework	Product-centric	Index/Indicator-based CVA, model/simulation-based CVA, DSS-based CVA, etc ...
L3	Specific Method	Architecture-centric	Gornitz's CVI index-based CVA, ICVI index-based CVA, etc ...

face persistent flooding that threatens their very existence (Aderinto, 2023; Delfino et al., 2023; Mollah et al., 2025; Wandres et al., 2023). Current data reveals that 10 % of global coasts face certain erosion, with 6.2 % experiencing severe rates exceeding 1 m per year (Bozzeda et al., 2023; Costa et al., 2024; Luijendijk et al., 2018), while coastal flooding disasters have already been doubled since the year 2000 (Nearing et al., 2024; Wei et al., 2022, 2023). The scale of human exposure remains critically high: approximately 600 million people inhabit low-lying coastal zones, with infrastructure valued at \$14.2 trillion now under escalating climate risks (Kirezci et al., 2020). Given these mounting challenges, quantifying coastal ecosystem vulnerability to climate change impacts has become essential for disaster prevention through strategic planning and targeted interventions (Zhang et al., 2024). Effective assessment frameworks must integrate quantitative analysis, clear communication, and interdisciplinary perspectives to generate actionable insights for policymakers and communities (Roukounis and Tsihrintzis, 2022). Such approaches aim to identify high-risk areas and establish priorities for developing robust adaptation and mitigation strategies (Rezvani et al., 2023).

Current methodologies for Coastal Vulnerability Assessment (CVA) span in three primary categories: index-based and indicator-based methods for regional analyses with static ranking results, dynamic computer model-based simulations for detailed site-specific cases, and GIS-based decision support interactive tools (DSS; Decision Support Systems) for ongoing decision support (Dey and Mazumder, 2023; Ramieri et al., 2011; Rizzo et al., 2025). To provide a better comprehension of CVAs, the following taxonomy system is introduced, influenced by the General System Theory (Ludwig von Bertalanffy, 1968), the scientific paradigms (Kuhn, 1996), and the falsifiable methods (Popper, 2005).

Despite this apparent diversity of CVA methods, the available tools and software relating to automation, streamlining and assistance on applying CVAs remain limited, with a notable absence of user-friendly platforms that can provide end-to-end automated workflows. For example, the Monitoring Integrated System for Land Degradation (MISLAND, 2020), while providing valuable land degradation monitoring capabilities across Africa, requires extensive manual preprocessing in QGIS desktop software for its coastal vulnerability index components, including manual rasterization, classification, and parameter assignment before data can be uploaded to the platform. Click or tap here to enter text. Similarly, the widely used InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs) coastal vulnerability model from the Natural Capital Project, though offering semi-automated calculations, remains desktop-dependent and demands significant manual data preparation and technical expertise (Project Natural Capital, 2024).

Other prominent tools face comparable limitations: the Dynamic Interactive Vulnerability Assessment (DIVA) model serves primarily academic research with complex setup requirements (Hinkel and Klein, 2009); HAZUS-MH from FEMA provides multi-hazard analysis but requires desktop GIS software and extensive manual configuration (FEMA, 2025); SimCLIM offers sophisticated climate modeling capabilities yet remains a proprietary commercial platform requiring specialized training (ClimSystems, 2025); and the Sea Level Affecting Marshes Model (SLAMM) focuses specifically on wetland environments through desktop-only applications (NOAA, 2025). Additional tools like the

DSAS, CoastSat, SAET, and CET provide valuable shoreline extraction or shoreline change automations, thus streamlining single components of a CVA (Domazetović et al., 2021; Himmelstoss et al., 2018; Palomar-Vázquez et al., 2023; Vos et al., 2019). While cloud-based platforms like Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al., 2017) and ArcGIS Online (ESRI, 2025) enable large-scale geospatial analysis, they are general-purpose tools, requiring significant programming and software-related expertise to implement specific methodologies.

Some notable advances in automated coastal monitoring and modeling systems have emerged to address specific aspects of coastal risk management. The HYDROGUARD project (Aryal et al., 2011) developed an autonomous and automated system for monitoring coastal risks and water resources using intelligent buoys equipped with sensors and decision support systems. This system provides real-time monitoring capabilities for flooding, pollution, and marine submergence through decentralized, interoperable technologies. Similarly, NOAA's multiplatform automated on-demand modeling system for coastal storm surge (Mani et al., 2022) addresses the need for automated storm surge modeling including inland hydrology effects, providing researchers and emergency managers with rapid access to storm surge predictions through cloud-based computational resources.

A few modern studies though are responding to the need for automating and limiting labor-intensive and time-consuming work for CVAs, with current examples (e.g. Arasi et al., 2025; Wong et al., 2024) tackling the case of manual workflows for ground surveys. By these new approaches, the implementation speed and ease of application are benefited, while the outcomes become more reproducible and standardized, resulting from the algorithmic nature of the innovations. Collectively, these approaches demonstrate that current coastal vulnerability assessment methods are characterized by fragmented workflows, proprietary software and GIS dependencies, and limited accessibility. The need for accessible coastal vulnerability assessment tools extends across diverse user communities, each with varying technical backgrounds and requirements. Academic researchers require reproducible methodologies for scientific studies, coastal management professionals need practical tools for operational planning, environmental consultants demand efficient solutions for client projects, policymakers require accessible data for evidence-based decision-making, and educators and students need intuitive platforms for learning and teaching purposes.

The index-based assessments are the most favorable by researchers due to their ease of use, ease of understanding by decision-makers, and the consistent methodologies (Balica et al., 2012; Dey and Mazumder, 2023). Among the various CVA methodologies, the Coastal Vulnerability Index (CVI), introduced by (Gornitz, 1991) stands out as the one with the highest application, as more than 60 CVI case studies have been published from 1994, while in 2020, over 2000 papers were referring to the term (Cruz-Ramírez et al., 2024). Additionally, it is considered the most straightforward and effective one among the rest of the CVA methods (from all CVA frameworks), due to its simplicity, accessibility and ease of implementation (Kuleli and Bayazit, 2024; Van Zanten et al., 2023; Toumasi et al., 2024).

The application of the CVI was showcased by Thieler and Hammar-Klose (2000) computing the index derived from six coastal variables: coastal geomorphology, coastal slope, relative sea-level change, shoreline change rate, mean tidal range, and mean wave height. Relying though only on physical parameters does not capture the whole spectrum of vulnerability, meaning exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity (Estoque et al., 2023). In general, traditional approaches to CVI often fell short, lacking the integration of socioeconomic factors (Theocharidis et al., 2024) and showcasing low quality, due to availability of data acquisition and extensive aggregations (Krivova et al., 2024). Apart from the factors, the choice of mathematical formulation significantly impacts the index's sensitivity and reliability (Alcántara-Carrió et al., 2024). The original formula (the square root of the product of ranked variables divided by their number) is known to

produce distribution distortions (alterations to the frequency distribution of the calculated index values when compared to the input variables) due to sensitivity to the number of variables used (specifically higher than seven), and common out of range uninterpretable results (Cogswell et al., 2018). Alternative mathematic formulations, such as the geometric mean, demonstrate greater reliability by tackling these core problems (Gatdula and Blanco, 2024; Şen, 2025). Despite the widespread adoption and recognized effectiveness of the CVI methodology, a critical gap exists in the availability of accessible, automated, and user-friendly tools for its implementation. Current approaches require extensive manual workflows across multiple proprietary software platforms, creating barriers to reproducibility and standardization of CVI applications across case studies. This technological bottleneck significantly impedes the broader adoption and quality of coastal vulnerability assessments (Petropoulos et al., 2024).

This study addresses these limitations by introducing CVic (Coastal Vulnerability Index Compiler), which is to our knowledge the first web-based platform for automated CVI calculation. The application offers a User Interface for the workflow needed to perform a CVI calculation, while also acts as a wrapper of Coastal Vulnerability Indices, the characteristics of which (formula, variables, ranking tables) are unchanged to remain standard and authentic. Operating entirely within web browsers, CVic requires no software installation and provides cross-platform compatibility across different operating systems and devices, making it accessible to users regardless of their technical infrastructure or hardware constraints. The serverless design ensures security and data protection. The primary objective is to develop an easily and freely accessible application that provides an end-to-end dynamic workflow for coastal vulnerability assessment.

2. The CVic platform

2.1. Introduction to the application

The CVic application is an open-access website (<https://alexandrosliaskos.github.io/CVic/>) that enables users to perform a CVI case study through an automated workflow from the input data to the results and a feature-rich, easy-to-use User Interface (UI). An implementation of a CVI research requires the definition of the coastal Area of Interest (AoI), the spatial resolution of the data and results, the specific Index to be applied, and the values of the index's parameters distributed across the coastal zone. The AoI is the along-the-shore coastline region of interest, but the cross-shore extension towards the land depends on the type of CVA. For index-based methods, the shoreline (as a line) is preferred as an AoI due to computation and visualization simplicity (the variables included in the specific CVI, though, may characterize essential part of the inland coastal area too). The granularity of the coastline sets the level of detail and is associated with the spatial aggregation defined for the data of the parameters (The equal parts in which the shoreline is divided for computational and scale of research reasons, which settles the resolution of the shoreline). Finally, the index is characterized by its parameters and vulnerability ranking, settling the type of research that is going to be implemented and the corresponding environment. The application revolves around the automation of this workflow by offering the ability to upload directly shorelines or draw new ones, specifying the meters of segmentation length, selecting the index of preference, assigning the values for each parameter-segment/s, and thus getting the resulting CVI and additional statistics, charts and exports.

For compliance with standard CVA methods, the application has been developed to support a suite of peer-reviewed coastal vulnerability indices. In the current release, the traditional CVI (Thieler and Hammar-Klose, 1999) and the Integrated Coastal Vulnerability Index (ICVI) (Alcántara-Carrió et al., 2024) are included, with the former to related only to the physical aspects of vulnerability, while the latter incorporates environmental and social factors too. To understand more

intuitively the components of the index-based CVA methods, a general scheme for index-based assessments and an example of the Gornitz's traditional CVI ranking table is presented in the tables below.

2.2. System architecture and overview

The CVic web app is developed as a browser-based serverless Single Page Application (SPA) and deployed on GitHub pages, achieving in that way zero operational cost, a fast and responsive experience, and a cross-platform easy-to-access tool (see Table 3). The user interface and the component-based architecture are built upon the React.js framework with TypeScript, ensuring safety, maintainability, scalability, and reliability. Additionally, page navigation is implemented through React Router with hash-based routing to ensure compatibility with static hosting environments. The application operates entirely on the web for both persistent data storage and computational operations. Even if it appears as a regular website, it is a secure and client-centric environment with IndexedDB as the local-browser database. For data processing, external JavaScript packages are integrated, like *Leaflet* for interactive maps, *Turf.js* for spatial operations, *GeoTIFF.js* for images, and *Shapefile.js* for shapefiles. The main architectural design is showcased in the following flowchart (Fig. 1), and the technology stack is presented in an additional table (Table 4).

The source code is compiled and bundled using Vite, while also open source, available on [Github](https://github.com). The codebase follows an organized structure with a separation of concerns based on domains and functionality, and a naming convention of PascalCase filenames for components and camelCase for utilities as shown in the following table (Table 5).

As for the workflow, CVic is designed to follow the logical progression required for a user-based application of a CVI. This can be broken down to distinct sequential phases of 3 main stages; the Data Pre-processing, the CVI analysis and the Results and Exports, each building upon the previous outputs. Initially, the input data for the shoreline, which represents the AoI, are imported either directly or by the import of a satellite image and a manual digitization process for the creation of the shoreline. After that follows the segmentation of the shoreline by a user-defined segment length constant. On the CVI analysis, the user selects the CVI index of preference, assigns manually the ranking values for each variable on the interactive map with the shoreline, and the CVI results are automatically computed when the assignment is fully complete. Finally, the user is shown the results and has the options of exporting the CVI results data in a GeoJSON format and the Results page report on an HTML format. This workflow is presented in the following flowcharts (Figs. 2–4).

2.3. Core technical implementation

2.3.1. Data management

CVic utilizes *IndexedDB*, a browser-native database that can support several gigabytes of storage. All information remains on the user's browser and is preserved indefinitely, even after refreshes, tab closes, restarts or network disconnections for the given session. A session in the app is defined by the initialization of a new analysis, meaning that data/progress in the specific analysis is lost automatically (overwritten) only if a new analysis is started. The custom data system consists of two primary object stores: *shorelineData*, which records the progression of shoreline-related workflow data (GeoJSON-based), and *satelliteImages*, which manages raster files and their associated metadata (Binary + metadata). Within the *shorelineData* store, all records conform to a generic wrapper structure:

```
{id : string; data : FeatureCollection; timestamp : number}
```

This schema is applied with four distinct keys *current-shoreline*, *current-segments*, *current-parameters*, and *current-index*, each representing a specific stage or product of the workflow. The precise structure of each object stored under the 4 keys is presented in the following table

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the architectural design of the CVIC web app.

Table 2
General scheme for an index-based assessment ranking table.

Component	Description	Example
Domain/Category	A broad grouping for related parameters.	Geomorphology
Parameter	The specific variable or factor being measured.	Coastal Slope
Indicator	The specific metric used to quantify the parameter.	Percentage (%)
Rank/Score	The numerical value assigned to a specific level of the indicator (e.g., 1–5, 1–10).	1
Level/Class	A qualitative description of the rank (e.g., Very Low, Good, Unacceptable).	Very Low
Criteria/Threshold	The specific data values or ranges that correspond to each rank and level.	>14.7 %
Weight	A value assigned to each parameter to reflect its relative importance in the overall index.	Equal (1/x)

(Table 6), with each schema reflecting the specific data requirements and workflow stage. For the *satelliteImage* store, a similar wrapper structure is almost identical, though with a single difference of the *data* field being an object of the processed image and its metadata (Table 7). A single database instance is maintained throughout the application lifecycle to prevent conflicts and reduce overhead. Each workflow step updates the relevant JavaScript object by modifying or extending its fields and then persists the result under a standard key. All read and write operations are executed as atomic transactions, ensuring that incomplete or failed writes do not result in partial or corrupted data. The system uses the W3C Structured Clone Algorithm for automatic serialization of complex objects and utilizes the *idb* library to provide a modern, promise-based interface to *IndexedDB*, thereby enhancing code maintainability and reliability.

The IndexedDB service exposes 13 API methods for database operations, organized into four categories for the database lifecycle, Shoreline GeoJSON CRUD (Create-Read-Update-Delete), Satellite Imagery CRUD, and cross-store operations as shown in the table below (Table 8).

2.3.2. Indices and formulas

The implementation of the indices and the calculations follow a layered architecture that separates index definitions, parameter management, calculation engines, and data persistence. The Index Registry serves as the central management system, providing a unified interface for accessing the required data and utilities. Each index is implemented as a self-contained module with its own parameter definitions, ranking tables, and calculation methods, ensuring that the specific criteria of the standard indices are accurately preserved. The index definition scheme includes specific fields, such as the id, name, required parameters, available formulas, etc ... as shown in the following table (Table 9).

The parameter content is stored in lookup tables, which contain the

Table 3
Gornitz's Coastal Vulnerability Index (CVI) ranking table for the variables of Coastal Landform Type and Relative Sea Level Change.

Domain/Category	Parameter	Indicator	Rank/Score	Level/Class	Criteria/Threshold
Physical	Coastal landform type	Categorical	1	Very Low	Rocky, cliffed coasts/ Fiords/ Fiards
			2	Low	Medium cliffs/ Indented coasts
			3	Moderate	Low cliffs/ Glacial drift/ Alluvial plains
			4	High	Cobble beaches/ Estuary/ Lagoon
			5	Very High	Barrier beaches/ Sand beaches/ Salt marsh/ Mud flats/ Deltas/ Mangrove/ Coral reefs
Hydroclimate	Relative Sea Level Change	mm/yr	1	Very Low	<1.8 mm/yr
			2	Low	1.8–2.5 mm/yr
			3	Moderate	2.5–3.4 mm/yr
			4	High	3.4–4.6 mm/yr
			5	Very High	>4.6 mm/yr

ranking tables of each parameter. In that way, the criteria and ranking system of each parameter is configured, while the vulnerability ranking values, levels and color for each level are common across all indices and parameters (Tables 10 and 11) (see Table 2).

As for the calculations, the geometric mean for the Gornitz CVI and the arithmetic and geometric mean for the ICVI have been implemented defined as index-specific mathematical operations with the usage of the Math.js library (Table 12).

Table 4
Technology Stack of the CVIc web application.

Component	Technology
Architecture	Serverless Single Page Application (SPA)
Frontend Core	React 18 + TypeScript
Build Tool	Vite + SWC Plugin
Routing	React Router (Hash Router)
Styling	Tailwind CSS + PostCSS
Interactive Maps	Leaflet + React-Leaflet
Charts & Graphs	ReCharts + Chart.js
Icons	Heroicons React
File Processing	Shapefile.js + GeoTIFF.js
Geo-Processing	Turf.js + GeoRaster
Report Generation	HTML2Canvas + DOM-to-Image
Data Storage	IndexedDB + idb Wrapper
Deployment	GitHub Pages
Browser Support	ES2020 (Chrome 80+, Firefox 72+, Safari 13.1+)

2.3.3. Satellite image processing

Uploading and visualizing satellite images within web applications is challenging but can be achieved by converting them into web-compatible raster objects. In CVIc, this has been accomplished for *GeoTIFF* images through an algorithmic pipeline optimized for memory efficiency and performance. Initially, binary data are extracted from uploaded *GeoTIFF* or *Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF (COG)* files using the *Web API's* `arrayBuffer()` method. The *GeoTIFF* library's `fromArrayBuffer()` function then parses coordinate system metadata and spatial reference information, while `getBoundingBox()` extracts precise geographic boundaries essential for accurate georeferencing. The core transformation utilizes the *GeoRaster* library's `fromArrays()` method to generate raster objects suitable for browser-based display, preserving spatial integrity.

To optimize performance, the system implements a 1:1000 sampling ratio, analyzing every thousandth pixel to determine minimum and maximum values for dynamic range adjustment, while excluding

Table 5
CVIc's codebase directory structure and naming convention.

Directory	Purpose	Naming Convention	Examples
<code>src/components/</code>	React components organized by domain	PascalCase	ParameterAssignmentPage.tsx, CviFormulaPanel.tsx
<code>src/components/common/</code>	Reusable UI components	PascalCase	ErrorBoundary.tsx, ErrorAlert.tsx, DebugPanel.tsx
<code>src/components/layout/</code>	Layout and structural components	PascalCase	Layout.tsx, Footer.tsx
<code>src/components/maps/</code>	Map-related components	PascalCase	DrawableMap.tsx, EnhancedLeafletMap.tsx, GeoRasterLeafletMap.tsx
<code>src/components/parameters/</code>	Parameter management components	PascalCase	ParameterValuePanel.tsx, MapInteractionPanel.tsx, SegmentTablePanel.tsx
<code>src/components/results/</code>	Results display components	PascalCase	CviCharts.tsx, CviLegend.tsx
<code>src/pages/</code>	Page-level components	PascalCase	AOISelectionPage.tsx, ParameterAssignmentPage.tsx, ResultsPage.tsx
<code>src/services/</code>	Data processing and external services	camelCase	imageProcessor.ts, indexedDBService.ts, shapefileProcessor.ts
<code>src/utills/</code>	Utility functions and helpers	camelCase	cviCalculations.ts, mapCapture.ts, geometry.ts, reportGenerator.ts
<code>src/types/</code>	TypeScript type definitions	camelCase	index.ts, indexSpecificTypes.ts, global.d.ts
<code>src/config/</code>	Configuration files and constants	camelCase	coastalIndices.ts, formulas.ts, standardParameters.ts
<code>src/logic/</code>	Business logic and complex calculations	camelCase	compositeFormulas.ts, valueAssignmentLogic.ts
<code>src/hooks/</code>	Custom React hooks	camelCase	useParameterAssignmentData.ts

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the workflow of the Data Pre-processing stage of the CVIc application. The pink boxes represent the actions and selections needed by the user, the green boxes the automatic processing, the yellow boxes the data uploads and the blue boxes the optional selections.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of the workflow of the CVI Analysis stage of the CVIc application. The pink boxes represent the actions and selections needed by the user, the green boxes the automatic processing, and the blue boxes the optional selections.

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the workflow of the Results and Export stage of the CVIc application. The pink boxes represent the actions and selections needed by the user, the green boxes the automatic processing, and the blue boxes the optional selections.

Table 6
Unified Comparative Schema Table for shorelineData Store.

Field	Type	current-shoreline	current-segments	current-parameters	current-index	Description
id	string	✓	✓	✓	✓	Key for the object (e.g., "current-shoreline")
data.type	"FeatureCollection"	✓	✓	✓	✓	GeoJSON collection identifier
data.features [].type	"Feature"	✓	✓	✓	✓	GeoJSON feature identifier
data.features [].geometry.type	"LineString"	✓	✓			Geometry type (for shoreline and segments)
data.features [].geometry.coordinates	number[][]	✓	✓			Array of [longitude, latitude] points
data.features [].properties.name	string	✓		✓	✓	Name or label (shoreline segment, parameter, or index)
data.features [].properties.id	string		✓	✓	✓	Unique identifier (segment, parameter, or index)
data.features [].properties.length	number		✓			Geodesic length of the segment
data.features [].properties.parameters	Record < string, number >		✓			Map of parameter-ID to assigned value
data.features [].properties.vulnerabilityIndex	number		✓			Computed vulnerability index
data.features [].properties.vulnerabilityFormula	string		✓			Identifier of the formula used
data.features [].properties.enabled	boolean			✓		Whether the parameter is enabled
data.features [].properties.type	string			✓		Value type: "categorical" or "numerical"
data.features [].properties.values_classification	Array<{ value: number, description: string }>			✓		Allowed categorical values for parameters
data.features [].properties.formula	string				✓	Formula identifier for the index
timestamp	number	✓	✓	✓	✓	Unix ms timestamp when this entry was last written

Table 7
Schema Table for satelliteImages Store.

Field	Type	Description
id	string	Unique identifier for the image (e.g., "image-1678886800000-abcdef")
data.id	string	Image identifier (matches the top-level id)
data.name	string	Original filename (e.g., "sentinel_image.tif")
data.url	string	Blob URL for accessing the image in the browser
data.bounds	number[] (length 4)	Bounding box: [minLon, minLat, maxLon, maxLat]
data.metadata.size	number	File size in bytes
data.metadata.type	string	MIME type (e.g., "image/tiff")
timestamp	number	Unix ms timestamp when this entry was created or last updated

NoData values that could distort visualization. This approach reduces computational overhead compared to full-image analysis yet maintains statistical representativeness for accurate 8-bit color depth conversion.

The final step creates a *Blob* object containing the processed raster data, which is stored in *IndexedDB*. The application generates a temporary Object URL using the browser's *URL.createObjectURL()* API, enabling direct integration of the raster image into the map interface. Memory management is handled automatically by revoking these URLs with *URL.revokeObjectURL()* when they are no longer needed. The implementation supports WGS84 (EPSG:4326) coordinate systems and processes up to three spectral bands, ensuring compatibility with standard Earth observation products such as Sentinel and Landsat satellite images. Notably, the actual raster data are stored as binary *Blobs* in *IndexedDB*, while the metadata and a Blob URL reference are maintained in the application's data schema for efficient retrieval and visualization.

2.3.4. Shoreline segmentation

After the upload of the shoreline, its spatial resolution should be

Table 8
IndexedDB's Service API methods specifications.

Method	Type	Purpose
<i>initialize()</i>	<i>Lifecycle</i>	Initialize database connection with version management
<i>deleteDatabase()</i>	<i>Lifecycle</i>	Private - Complete database removal
<i>resetDatabase()</i>	<i>Lifecycle</i>	Dev Utility - Reset database to clean state
<i>storeShorelineData()</i>	<i>Shoreline CRUD</i>	Store GeoJSON shoreline data with timestamp
<i>getShorelineData()</i>	<i>Shoreline CRUD</i>	Retrieve shoreline data by ID
<i>deleteShorelineData()</i>	<i>Shoreline CRUD</i>	Delete specific shoreline record
<i>clearAllShorelineData()</i>	<i>Shoreline CRUD</i>	Delete all shoreline records
<i>storeSatelliteImage()</i>	<i>Image CRUD</i>	Store satellite image with metadata
<i>getSatelliteImage()</i>	<i>Image CRUD</i>	Retrieve single satellite image
<i>getAllSatelliteImages()</i>	<i>Image CRUD</i>	Retrieve all satellite images
<i>deleteSatelliteImage()</i>	<i>Image CRUD</i>	Delete specific satellite image
<i>clearAllSatelliteImages()</i>	<i>Image CRUD</i>	Delete all satellite images
<i>clearAllData()</i>	<i>System</i>	Clear both shoreline and image stores

configured and the way to accomplish that is by transforming the initial polyline into a series of discrete, analysis-ready segments. This process is implemented using a combination of open-source geospatial libraries and custom application logic. The segmentation workflow begins with a *GeoJSON* representation of the shoreline, which may consist of single or multiple line features. For geospatial processing, the *Turf.js* library (*Turf, 2013*) is utilized, which stands as a popular modern approach for web-based geo-computations (*Netek et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2025*). The core geospatial operations are performed using the *Turf.js*'s *turf.length* function to calculate the geodesic length of each line feature. The number of required segments is determined by dividing the total length by the user-defined resolution.

To achieve uniform segmentation, the application applies *turf.lineSliceAlong* (*Turf, 2025a*), which interpolates breakpoints at precise

Table 9
Index Definition scheme of the CVIc application.

Property	Type	Purpose	CVI	ICVI
id	string	Unique identifier	'cvi-thieler-1999'	'icvi-alcantara-2024'
name	string	Full index name	'Coastal Vulnerability Index (CVI)'	'Integrated Coastal Vulnerability Index (ICVI)'
shortName	string	Abbreviated name	'CVI'	'ICVI'
type	string	Index classification	'true-index'	'composite-index'
citation	string	Research reference	Thieler and Hammar-Klose (1999)	Alcántara-Carrió et al. (2024)
requiredParameters	array	Parameter definitions	6 physical parameters	12 parameters (6 EVI + 6 SVI)
validationRules	array	Validation specifications	Parameter count, weights	Parameter count, weight sum, formula compatibility
resultClassification	object	Vulnerability ranges	1.0–5.0 scale	0.0–1.0 scale (dual ranges)
availableFormulas	array	Supported calculations	Geometric mean only	Arithmetic & geometric mean

Table 10
Vulnerability Ranking lookup table scheme of a parameter.

Field	Data Type	Purpose	Example Value	Notes
value	number	Vulnerability ranking score	1, 2, 3, 4, 5	Integer scale 1-5
criteria	string	Parameter value/condition	"0.55–0.85 m", "Rocky, cliffed coasts"	Text description of when to use this ranking
label	string	Vulnerability Ranking description/classification	"Very Low"	Common vulnerability levels across parameters and indices
color	string	Hex color code for visualization	"#1a9850"	Common colors across parameters and indices

Table 11
Vulnerability ranking level coloring system of the application.

Ranking Level	Ranking Value	Visual Representation
Very Low	1	Green
Low	2	Light Green
Moderate	3	Yellow
High	4	Orange
Very High	5	Red

geodesic intervals and extracts the corresponding line segments. This methodology is grounded in spatial sampling theory, specifically systematic sampling design, which provides optimal spatial coverage and minimizes sampling bias when dealing with spatially autocorrelated features (Madow, 1953). The systematic placement of sampling points at equal intervals along linear geographic features has been established as more efficient than random sampling strategies for spatially distributed data (Delmelle, 2014). This approach preserves the spatial fidelity and

Table 12
Index formulas definition in the CVIc application.

Formula ID	Mathematical Expression	Description	Implementation
cvi-geometric	$CVI = \sqrt[n]{\prod_{i=1}^n V_i}$	Geometric mean with equal weights	Math.pow(product, 1/n)
icvi-arithmetic	$ICVI = \frac{EVI + SVI}{2}$ $EVI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^6 V_i}{6}, SVI = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^6 V_j}{6}$	Arithmetic mean of sub-indices	(eviSum/6 + sviSum/6)/2
icvi-geometric	$ICVI = \frac{EVI + SVI}{2}$ $EVI = \sqrt[6]{\prod_{i=1}^6 V_i}, SVI = \sqrt[6]{\prod_{j=1}^6 V_j}$	Geometric mean of sub-indices	(Math.pow(eviProduct, 1/6) + Math.pow(sviProduct, 1/6))/2

curvature of the original shoreline geometry. Each segment becomes a new *GeoJSON* feature with a unique identifier, and annotated with attributes such as its index, parent line reference, and exact length.

2.3.5. Interactive parameter assignment

Interactive parameter assignment is achieved through a combination of spatial filtering and persistent data management. Each shoreline segment is represented as a *GeoJSON* Feature, with its geometry defined as either a *LineString* or *MultiLineString* and already stored in the *IndexedDB*'s *shorelineData* store. When a user draws a selection area in the map, the input is converted to a *GeoJSON* Polygon and *Turf.js*'s *booleanIntersects* function (Turf, 2025b) is used to determine which segment geometries intersect the selection polygon.

Each segment maintains a specific collection of values assigned for each parameter, with each parameter having an identifier (ID) as key for lookup. The values include the parameter type, assigned value, and vulnerability score. Parameter value options are predefined in a file configuration, which contains categorical options arrays and numerical vulnerability ranges for each parameter type. When selecting values from the dropdown interface, the system retrieves these predefined options from the parameter's configuration and allows assignment to selected segments. Upon value assignment, the system updates each selected segment's parameter map and persists the modified segment collection to *IndexedDB*.

2.4. User interface demonstration

2.4.1. Shoreline source selection

Users start the workflow by selecting their preferred method for providing shoreline data. The application offers two primary options: uploading existing shoreline data or creating new shoreline through digitization. For existing data, users can upload zipped Shapefiles containing *LineString* or *MultiLineString* geometries. The digitization option enables users to upload *GeoTIFF* satellite imagery and manually trace shoreline features using interactive drawing tools (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Shoreline Source Selection Page: Page for user selection for the shoreline input, either by uploading an existing zipped Shapefile of the shoreline or by creating a new one, with the upload of a satellite image and the digitization of the coastline upon it.

2.4.2. Shoreline data processing

During the data processing phase, uploaded *Shapefile* shoreline files are converted to *GeoJSON* geometric features using the *ShpJS* library. For satellite imagery uploads, *GeoTIFF* files are transformed into web-compatible visualizations. The processed shoreline data are stored in *IndexedDB* under the *current-shoreline* key (Figs. 6–8).

2.4.3. Shoreline segmentation

In the segmentation phase, the shoreline is split into discrete parts. Users define the spatial resolution by specifying segment length in meters, with the system automatically handling the operations. Each generated segment is stored under the *current-segment* key (Fig. 9).

Fig. 6. Shoreline Upload Page: Page for the upload of the zipped Shapefile shoreline and automatic preview.

2.4.4. Segment review

The segment review phase provides users with tabular and spatial visualization of generated shoreline segments. The interface presents segment statistics including total count, individual lengths, and spatial distribution through an interactive map display. Users can examine/review individual segments through click-based selection, with the map automatically zooming to selected features (Fig. 10).

2.4.5. Index and parameter selection

During this phase, users select their preferred Coastal Vulnerability Index approach from standardized options including the traditional CVI (Thieler and Hammar-Klose, 1999) and the Integrated Coastal Vulnerability Index (ICVI) (Alcántara-Carrió et al., 2024). Each index includes predefined parameter sets with associated vulnerability ranking tables, and mathematical formulations. The system displays detailed parameter information including vulnerability criteria, ranking scales, and categorical classifications, enabling informed selection based on research objectives and data availability (Fig. 11).

2.4.6. Parameter value assignment and CVI calculation

The parameter assignment phase represents the core analytical component of the workflow. Users assign vulnerability values to shoreline segments through multiple interaction methods: individual segment selection, area-based selection using polygon drawing tools, or table entries selections. The interface provides dedicated panels for parameter and parameter value selection, with dropdown menus that contain predefined categorical or numerical vulnerability input fields. Users assign the values for a parameter on the desired segments, while they can also visualize assignment progress through completion percentages and real-time colored-coded segments on the map and table updates. Following the parameter values strictly complete assignment, the CVI calculation process applies the selected mathematical formulation to compute vulnerability scores for each segment (Figs. 12 and 13).

2.4.7. Results visualization and export

The final phase presents calculated CVI results through interactive maps, statistical summaries, and export capabilities. The map interface displays shoreline segments with color-coded symbology based on vulnerability categories (Very Low to Very High), enabling spatial pattern identification and hotspot detection. Statistical panels provide summary metrics including minimum, maximum, and average CVI values, along with categorical distributions across vulnerability levels. The application offers multiple export formats like a *GeoJSON* for the CVI results and an *HTML* report for saving the Results page (Fig. 14).

2.5. Application prerequisites

As already mentioned, the application requires no installation, authentication, subscription fees, or any other constraint. It is deployed as a website, and the source code is open-sourced. It is cross-platform, independent from Operating Systems and even fully compatible with mobile devices. Regarding the application requirements, CVIc accepts two primary input data types for coastal vulnerability assessments. Users must provide either zipped Shapefiles containing *LineString* or *MultiLineString* geometries representing coastal shorelines, or satellite *GeoTIFF* imagery for manual shoreline digitization using interactive drawing tools. The digitization workflow requires *GeoTIFF* format with geographic coordinate system metadata, WGS84 coordinate reference system compatibility, and supports up to three spectral bands for optimal visualization, with Cloud Optimized *GeoTIFF* format recommended for enhanced performance. Required input data are readily available through open-access sources. Satellite imagery can be obtained from ESA's Copernicus Browser for Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data and USGS's *EarthExplorer* for Landsat archive, while shorelines can be digitized through free and open-source GIS software like QGIS.

A final requirement involves user expertise in vulnerability

Fig. 7. Satellite Image Upload Page: Page for uploading GeoTIFF and Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF satellite images.

Fig. 8. Digitize Shoreline Page: Page for visualization of the updated satellite image and drawing capabilities for digitizing the shoreline.

Fig. 9. Shoreline Segmentation Page: Page to define the length the desired spatial resolution that should be achieved on the shoreline.

Fig. 10. Segments Review Page: Page to preview and inspect the generated shoreline segments in the map.

distribution assessment along the case-study coastline. This methodology necessitates understanding of study area vulnerability characteristics, and access to relevant geological, oceanographic, and socioeconomic data. All requirements of the CVIc implementation are summarized below (Table 13).

3. Current limitations and future developments

While CVIc represents a significant advancement in automated coastal vulnerability assessment and geospatial sciences, several limitations present opportunities for future enhancement. This section examines technical constraints, methodological restrictions, and planned developments that will expand the platform’s capabilities.

The current technical implementation is not configured for

optimizations, but functionality, thus the fixes of these limitations will be introduced in updated versions of the website. The most critical limitation of the platform is the processing of extensive shoreline datasets during segmentation operations. JavaScript’s inherently single-threaded architecture means that computationally intensive synchronous geometric processing blocks the main thread, rendering the user interface unresponsive and potentially causing browser crashes. Additionally, image rendering responsiveness presents small delays when trying to zoom-in and out. This is caused by the computational overhead of dynamically resampling and rendering raster tiles on the main JavaScript thread during map navigation. While libraries like georaster-layer-for-leaflet provide functionality, they can struggle with large, unoptimized rasters (GeoTIFF, 2025). These constraint can be mitigated by implementing Web Workers, which enable "labor-intensive

Fig. 11. Index Selection Page: Page to select the coastal vulnerability index of preference for the case study.

Fig. 12. Value Assignment Page: Page to assign values to the segments of each parameter of the selected CVI.

processing to be performed in a separate thread, allowing the main (usually the UI) thread to run without being blocked" (Mozilla Developer Network, 2025).

Apart from technical issues, there are also methodological constraints. The parameter value assignment refers to the core data of a CVI case study and the replacement of the manual current approach (the assignment of the values in an interactive map) would be a major

update. The difficulty though arises from the plurality of the parameters (Roukounis and Tsihrintzis, 2022), the global spatial extension and limit of existing reliable databases and techniques. Also, the platform currently implements two standardized CVI methodologies: the traditional (Thieler and Hammar-Klose, 2000) CVI and the Integrated Coastal Vulnerability Index (ICVI) by (Alcántara-Carrió et al., 2024). While these indices cover primary research applications, the scientific

Fig. 13. CVI Calculation: Tab on the Value Assignment Page to calculate the CVI and continue to the results.

Fig. 14. Results Page: Page to visualize the calculated CVI and the automated generated statistics with the options to export the results in a GeoJSON or the results page in an HTML report.

Table 13
Requirements for the application of a CVI case study on the CVIc platform.

Category	Requirement	Details
Data Types	Zipped Shapefiles	LineString or MultiLineString geometries
	GeoTIFF Imagery	For manual shoreline digitization
GeoTIFF Specs	Format	Geographic coordinate system metadata required
	CRS	WGS84 compatibility required
Expertise	Bands	Up to 3 spectral bands supported
	Optimization	Cloud Optimized GeoTIFF
	User Knowledge	Understanding of study area vulnerability
	Data Access	Geological, oceanographic, socioeconomic data

community has introduced a lot more (Cruz-Ramírez et al., 2024) and the aim for the platform is to incorporate as many as possible, given that they are popular among researchers and case studies. Moreover, the manual shoreline digitization could be automated with the extraction of the coastlines with satellite imagery spectral analysis, as seen with CoastSat, SAET, and CET (Domazetović et al., 2021; Palomar-Vázquez et al., 2023; Vos et al., 2019), resulting in the user’s single input requirement of the Area of Interest (AoI).

Finally, the application is planned to be integrated into the in-development EO-PERSIST platform (<https://eo-persist.eu/>). EO-PERSIST project (Earth Observation Data for Promoting Research & SocioEconomic Impact from Satellite Technologies) is a 48-month research initiative funded under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant agreement No. 101086386)

(EO-PERSIST, 2023). It is dedicated to understanding climate change impacts in Arctic and sub-Arctic regions through permafrost monitoring while building upon previous European initiatives such as Copernicus and HORIZON-CL4-2021 that have already completed on frameworks for EO data collection and distribution (European Commission, 2023). The project aims to create a cloud-based platform for processing Earth Observation (EO) data while connecting raw satellite information directly to environmental monitoring systems and supporting decision-making processes.

4. Final remarks

This study presents the newly developed CVIc (Coastal Vulnerability Index Compiler), the first web-based geoprocessing platform for automated coastal vulnerability assessment. CVIc development is driven from the need of eliminating the fragmented workflows and proprietary software dependencies that have historically limited the accessibility and reproducibility of CVI methodologies. Towards this direction, CVIc addresses the critical gap between complex manual processes requiring multiple desktop GIS applications and the urgent need for accessible vulnerability assessment tools, particularly given the escalating coastal crisis evidenced by 393 natural disasters in 2024 alone, resulting in 16,753 fatalities and \$320 billion in economic losses (CRED, 2025b). By integrating client-side data processing with browser-based geospatial operations, the platform successfully produced a unified end-to-end workflow spanning from shoreline data input to results visualization and export.

The availability of CVIc marks a significant contribution to the fields of geospatial and coastal sciences, as a practical user application, addressing the gap of translating research into accessible tools for end-users. Additionally, it stands as a web application for geospatial analysis, a case rarely seen with the dominance of desktop software (Netek et al., 2023). It has already been tested with various dataset sizes and under different computational environments, demonstrating capability to process up to 100,000 shoreline segments while maintaining performance standards comparable to desktop applications. CVIc's primary contribution which is anticipated to shape the future development of scientific software engineering in geoinformatics, is the architecture that demonstrates how complex geoprocessing can be fully and freely implemented in the web, maintaining computational performance, how applications can be deployed with no cost as websites, and how client-side technologies can handle large datasets, while at the same time provide data privacy and security.

The CVIc platform has transformed traditionally fragmented multi-software workflows into a streamlined single-platform process dedicated to a scientific field of research, greatly improving the practicality and usability for diverse user communities including academic researchers, coastal managers, environmental consultants, policymakers, and educational institutions. Despite the important advantages offered by the CVIc platform and its significant contribution towards complete automation of CVI workflows, certain limitations remain to be addressed, which are at the focal point of our research. For example, the current version requires manual parameter value assignment for each coastal segment, as the tool does not yet allow automated acquisition of vulnerability parameter values from global databases or remote sensing products. In addition, a further limitation is the platform's current restriction to only two standard CVI methodologies. In this context, future efforts should focus on refining the platform to address these limitations through automated parameter acquisition systems, integration of additional vulnerability indices, and implementation of advanced performance optimizations. Developments would improve CVIc's practical usefulness for operational coastal management and monitoring applications. These directions of development form key objectives for the platform's continued evolution as an open-source tool for coastal vulnerability index-based assessment.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alexandros Liaskos: Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **George P. Petropoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Niki Evelpidou:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Data curation. **Spyridon E. Detsikas:** Writing – review & editing.

Software and data availability

Name of Software/Platform: CVIc (Coastal Vulnerability Index Compiler).

Developer: Alexandros Liaskos.

First year available: 2025.

Software version: 0.1.0.

Size of archive: 66 mb.

Program language: TypeScript.

Software requirements: Modern web browser with JavaScript enabled (Chrome 90+, Firefox 88+, Safari 14+, Edge 90+).

Hardware requirements: 4 GB RAM, 500 MB browser storage; internet connection for map tiles.

Software Availability <https://alexandrosliaskos.github.io/CVIc/>

Data/source code availability: <https://github.com/AlexandrosLiaskos/CVIc> (MIT License).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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